

MALICIOUS SOFTWARE

Kubaev Asaliddin Esirgapovich

Assistant of the Samarkand State Medical Institute

Ismoilova Ug'iloy Baxtiyorovna

Student of Samarkand State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7615194>

Abstract: This article describes the types and types of malicious software that have become known worldwide today, as well as their behavior in computer programs or ways of causing damage.

Keywords: Trojan Horses, Adware, Spyware, Backdoors Trigger, Logic Bombs, Logging Authentication Requests, Semi-Resident Viruses.

Introduction: Malware is any program designed to cause harm to a computer, server, client, or computer network.

Malware is defined as a tool intended to perform malicious actions without the user's permission, such as an attacker, and may take the form of executable code (.exe), active content, scripts, or other forms. An attacker can use malicious software to discredit system security, disrupt computer operations, collect confidential information, modify, delete or add content on a website, gain control over a user's computer. In addition, malware can be used to obtain large amounts of confidential information from government organizations and corporate organizations.

Types of malware:

- viruses: a self-replicating program that attaches itself to another program, the computer's boot sector, or a document.
- Trojan horses: at first glance, they appear as good and useful software, but they consist of hidden malicious code.
- Adware: Software that tracks a user's browsing behavior for marketing purposes or to serve ads.
- Spyware: software code that captures user information and sends it to an attacker.
- Rootkits: this malicious software hides certain actions to avoid being detected by the operating system.
- Backdoors: are malicious software codes that allow an attacker to bypass authentication, such as gaining privileges without an administrator password.
- logic bombs: a malicious software tool that executes its action when a logical condition is met.
- Botnet: Discredited computers on the Internet used by an attacker to launch distributed attacks.
- Ransomware: this malware encrypts or locks valuable files on the victim's computer and demands payment.

A logic bomb

There is no self-replication

Increment: nil

Contagiousness: possible

A logic bomb is a two-part code:

1. The payload portion is the action portion for execution. The payload part can look like anything you want, but the damaging effect will have meaning.

2. A trigger controls the execution of the payload portion as a logical condition and is evaluated. The exact trigger condition is limited by imagination and is based on local conditions such as date, user login, or operating system version. In this way, triggers can be designed to be remotely configurable or not based on the availability of a certain state.

Logic bombs can be embedded within existing code or stand-alone. A typical parasitic (infectious) example is shown below, which can cause a computer crash when a specific date is used as a trigger:

```
legitimate code
```

```
if date is Friday the 13th:
```

```
crash_computer( )
```

```
legitimate code
```

```
Trojan
```

```
Self reproduction: no
```

```
Increment: nil
```

```
Contagiousness: Yes
```

This type of malware is based on a trick used during the war between the Greeks and the Trojans, hence the name.

In information and communication technology, a Trojan horse is a program designed to perform some simple task. However, it performs an additional damaging function in secret. A classic example is a login password capture program possible, it records authentication requests such as "username" and "password" and waits for information to be entered by the user. When this happens, the password catcher will write down passwords for its creator, then issue an "invalid password" message before actually logging in. An unsuspecting user will appear to have made a mistake.

```
Backdoors
```

```
Self reproduction: no
```

```
Increment: nil
```

```
Contagiousness: Available
```

A backdoor is any mechanism that can pass a simple security check. Developers sometimes create a backdoor (hole) for legitimate reasons.

Backdoor (hole) programs, such as logic bombs, can also be in program code or in standalone programs. An example of a backdoor (hole) is shown in the code below, which bypasses the login authentication process. username = read_username ()

```
password = read_password ( )
```

```
if username is "133t h4ck0r":
```

```
return ALLOW_LOGIN
```

```
if username and password are valid:
```

```
return ALLOW_LOGIN
```

```
else:
```

```
return DENY_LOGIN
```


Virus

Self-replication: yes

Increase in number: positive

Contagiousness: yes

A computer virus is a type of malicious software that reproduces itself by modifying and injecting its own code into other computer programs during execution. If this process is successful, the affected area is said to be "infected" with a computer virus.

Virus creators use social engineering tricks and detailed information about security vulnerabilities to initially infect systems and spread the virus. Most computer viruses target systems running the Microsoft Windows OS and use many mechanisms to infect new hosts and many

In some cases, it uses anti-detection/stealth strategies to evade antivirus tools.

Currently, there is no single systematic classification of computer viruses, and different sources classify them based on different factors. In particular, computer viruses can be classified according to the following factors:

1. According to the way resources are used. Currently, it is appropriate to divide computer viruses into virus-parasites (or just viruses) and virus-worms (or just worms) according to the way they use resources.

The first way to multiply using resources is to belong to another program. For example, they are implemented inside other programs and are activated when that program is loaded. The latter usually use only the resources of the computing system (fast and non-volatile memory, non-program files) and distribute their copies over the network, distributed to everyone using messengers, memory buffers and foreign archives. Worms are autonomous and do not attach to other programs.

2. According to the type of damaged objects. "Macros" or "scripts" written in a certain programming language and contained in various office applications - MS Word document, MS Excel spreadsheet, Corel Draw image, files serve as a means of creating conditions for macroviruses. Examples of this are the Concept virus that infects MS Word documents and the Laroux virus that infects Excel spreadsheets.

Multi-platform viruses infect different objects at the same time. For example, the OneHalf.3544 virus infects both MS-DOS programs and the boot sectors of the hard disk, while viruses belonging to the Anarchy family can infect MS-DOS and Windows programs as well as MS Word documents. "Macros" or "scripts" written in a certain programming language and contained in various office applications - MS Word document, MS Excel spreadsheet, Corel Draw image, files serve as a means of creating conditions for macroviruses. Examples of this are the Concept virus that infects MS Word documents and the Laroux virus that infects Excel spreadsheets.

Multi-platform viruses infect different objects at the same time. For example, the OneHalf.3544 virus infects both MS-DOS programs and the boot sectors of the hard disk, while viruses belonging to the Anarchy family can infect MS-DOS and Windows programs as well as MS Word documents.

3. According to the principle of activation. According to this feature, it is recommended to divide viruses into resident and non-resident types. Resident viruses are always located in the computer's memory in an active state, to the victim

It follows requests from another program or operating system and then infects it. For example, executable programs are damaged during loading, during termination, or during the transfer of their files. Examples of these are viruses OneHalf.3544 (in MS-DOS environment) and Win9X.CIH (in Windows 95/98/ME environment). Non-resident viruses are activated during the startup of the infected media and have a limited lifetime. For example, the Vienna.648 virus starts immediately after the infected program is launched. However, at this time, it manages to find many victims from the disk and attach them. After that, it transfers control to its keeper and itself "sleeps" until the next boot.

Multi-tasking operating systems have "semi-resident" viruses that load like non-resident viruses. Organized as programs loaded in separate streams, it behaves like a resident during the entire execution of these programs and completes its work together with the host program. An example of this is Win32.Funlove.4070.

4. According to the program code organization approach. These taxonomic characters make it possible to distinguish viruses into encrypted, non-encrypted and polymorphic.

Unencrypted viruses pretend to be normal programs and do not have any additional operations in the program code. Such viruses (such as Vienna.648) can be easily detected in programs and can be researched and removed by disassemblers and decompilers. There will be several changes in the code of encrypted viruses. Encrypted virus is first decrypted in the memory of the computing device and then starts to damage. Therefore, it is difficult to identify, study and delete these viruses, and this complexity is characterized at least by the reverse operation in it - decoding the code. Usually, virus encryption is done by using a special anti-debugger method in the code. Sayha.Diehard virus can be included among such viruses.

Polymorphic viruses are encoded viruses of different forms that change their binary form from copy to copy. OneHalf family viruses can be included in this class of viruses. In special cases, polymorphic viruses are metamorphic viruses that make copies of themselves without encoding their binary bodies, but only by changing them. An example of such viruses is the Win32.Zmyst virus.

1. Classification of viruses and worms. The classification of viruses and worms is based on the ways of their spread. For example, mail worms (e.g. E-Worm.Win32.Aliz) are spread via e-mail, while network worms (commonly referred to as Internet worms) are spread using network protocols and transmitted either as packets of data (e.g. Net-Worm. Win32.Lovesan). And "telephone" or "mobile" worms (for example, Cabir) spread through different "networks". For example, through BlueTooth, which is considered a wireless data transmission network. Also, the type of file worms that spread in the 1980s (such as Mkworm.715) do not spread independently. Perhaps, it copies itself to different carriers and directories, even ZIP, RAR files, and distributes itself in that order.

6. Classification of computer viruses by other factors. In addition to the above factors, computer viruses can be classified based on the following factors:

- according to the malicious operating system and platform (DOS, Windows, Unix, Linux, Android);
- according to the programming language in which the computer virus was written (assembler, high-level programming language, Tenary language, etc.);
- according to additional malicious functions (trackers, keyloggers, spies, botnets, etc.).

Of course, the above classification of computer viruses is not final, and each author can analyze them based on the factors he chooses. In the next section, a lot of damage in computing networks is presented and the popular malicious software tools are introduced.

Virus history

For the first time, on November 11, 1983, American Fred Cohen, a student of the University of Southern California, gave a presentation of a computer virus that can multiply at a speed of 5 minutes to 1 hour.

A year later, Cohen writes a book about the dangers of viruses spreading across computer networks and the potential for creating antivirus software.

The first virus created (created in 1986) was called "Brain" and was spread only through computer diskettes. The first antivirus program was developed in 1988.

The 4 most powerful viruses of all time

1. ILOVE YOU

ILOVE YOU is one of the most powerful malware ever created. It wreaked havoc on computer systems worldwide and caused an estimated \$10 billion in damage. It is estimated that 10% of the world's computers are infected. Governments and large corporations have taken their mail systems offline to prevent infection.

The virus was created by two Filipino programmers, Reonel Ramones and Onel de Guzman. This virus used social engineering to get people to click on an "extra link". In this case, it was a request for a confession of love. The attachment was actually a script that was formatted as a TXT file. Because at that time Windows was hiding the actual extension of this file. After clicking the button, it sends itself to everyone on the user's mailing list and continues to overwrite the files. This puts the computer in a state where it cannot be turned off.

2. Code Red

Code Red first appeared in 2001 and was discovered by two employees of eEye Digital Security. It was named Code Red because the couple drank a drink called Code Red Mountain Dew during the discovery.

Exploiting a buffer overflow vulnerability in the system, it targeted computers with Microsoft's IIS web server installed. It leaves very little trace on hard memory. Because it can work in full memory, its size is 3569 bytes.

When infected, it starts to create a hundred copies, but due to a programming error, it reproduces again and ends up consuming a lot of system resources.

The most memorable symptom was the message it left on affected web pages saying "Attacked by the Chinese", which itself became a meme. A vaccine was later released and was later estimated to have caused up to \$2 billion in damage. A total of 1-2 million servers were affected. During this period, there were 6 million IIS servers.

3. Melissa

In 1999 David L. Created by Smith. This infected Word document was posted to a decentralized network group named alt.sex and claimed to be a list of passwords for pornographic sites. This is what people are interested in and it works when they download and open it.

The virus sends itself to 50 people in the e-mail address book, causing an increase in e-mail traffic. It disrupted the email services of governments and corporations. It also sometimes breaks the docs by adding a Simpsons (American animation genre) reference to them.

Smith was eventually caught handing over the Word document to him. The file was uploaded using a stolen AOL account, and with their help, law enforcement agencies were able to arrest him less than a week after the outbreak.

He cooperated with the FBI in catching other virus creators known as the creator of the Anna Kournikova virus. For his cooperation, he served only 20 months and paid a \$5,000 fine on top of the 10-year sentence. It was reported that the virus caused 80 million dollars in damage.

4. Sasser

The Windows OS worm was first discovered in 2004 by Sven Jaschan, the same student who created the Netsky worm. This worm exploited a buffer overflow vulnerability in the Local Security Authority Subsystem Service (LSASS). This allowed us to control the local account security policy that caused the computer to crash. It also uses system resources to distribute to other machines over the Internet and automatically infect others.

The virus has affected airlines, news agencies, public transport, hospitals and many other critical infrastructures, recording more than a million cases of infection. In total, the damage was 18 billion dollars. Jaschen was sentenced to 21 months probation on a juvenile conviction.

References:

1. Бабаш, А. В. Криптографические методы защиты информ.: Уч.пос.: Т.1/А.В.Бабаш- 2изд.-ИЦ РИОР,НИЦ ИНФРА-М,2016-413с(/ А.В. Бабаш. - Москва: Мир, 2016. - 597 с.
2. Баранова, Е. К. Информационная безопасность и защита. Учебное пособие / Е.К. Баранова, А.В. Бабаш. - М.: РИОР, Инфра-М, 2016. - 324 с.
3. Борисов, М. А. Основы организационно-правовой защиты информации / М.А. Борисов, О.А. Романов. - М.: Ленанд, 2014. - 248 с.
4. Борисов, М. А. Основы программно-аппаратной защиты информации / М.А. Борисов, И.В. Заводцев, И.В. Чижов. - М.: Либроком, 2013. - 376 с.
5. Варлатая, С. К. Криптографические методы и средства обеспечения информационной безопасности. Учебное пособие / С.К. Варлатая, М.В. Шаханова. - М.: Проспект, 2015. - 152 с.
6. Academic Research, Uzbekistan www.ares.uz formation of students ' skills in using the internet and hit the digital technologies. Kubaev A.E, Abdullaeva S. B
7. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(2), 748-751
<https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/1374>
8. Ахборот хавфсизлиги: асосий тушунчалар.Таҳдидлар ва уларнинг турлари. Ахборот хавфсизлиги сиёсати мавзусидаги маруза дарсни модул тизимида онлайн утиш. Kubaev A.E, Ne'matov N.I.
9. Хоразм Маъмун академияси ахборотномаси: илмий журнал.-№1 (85) 2022-2, Стр. – 290-300. <http://mamun.uz/uz/page/56>.
10. THE EASIEST RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CREATING A WEBSITE . Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. Kubaev A.E, Nematov.N.I
https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=eZdoKhkAAAAJ&citation_for_view=eZdoKhkAAAAJ:u-x6o8ySG0sC
11. Тиббий тасвир олишда радиология соҳасининг тавсифланиши. galaxy international interdisciplinary research journal. Kubaev A.E, Abdullaeva S. B
https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=eZdoKhkAAAAJ&citation_for_view=eZdoKhkAAAAJ:8k81kl-MbHgC
12. DESCRIPTION OF RADIOLOGY FIELD IN MEDICAL IMAGING. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal (MRJ). Volume: 01 Issue: 06 | 2022 ISSN: (2751-7543) Pages. 264-268. <https://innosci.org/wos/article/view/343/304> Germaniya.
13. The role of information technology in business.Eurasian journal of mathematical theory and computer sciences Innovative Academy Research Support Center UIF = 8.3 | SJIF = 5.916 www.in-academy.uz
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5584563>